

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.351 Max: 62.520	1441 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic

In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION construction cut of well 1449 + 1390	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1424	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1440
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX	
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble	<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine	<input type="checkbox"/> Ash		
<input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones		
<input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt	<input type="checkbox"/> Human bones		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs	<input type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand	<input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth		
<input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster	<input type="checkbox"/> Silt	<input type="checkbox"/> Shells		
<input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe	<input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)			
<input type="checkbox"/> Glass				
			Compaction	Color
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown
			<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Light Brown
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White
			<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red
			<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow
				<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts: 1390, 1449
Is covered by: 1424	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts: 1001
Is filled by: 1440	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: south central in area B well, north of SU1424

Shape: irregular linear cut running along well SU1390, 1448 and 1449

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify):

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:
irregular - is interrupted by bedrock near northeast corner, width increases in west

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Cut begins regularly along eastern side of wells ¹³⁹⁰⁺ 1449, cut curves to the west to follow well, suggesting that ¹³⁹⁰⁺ 1449 is indeed one continuous well. Halfway along east-west section of the cut, the edges become less defined and debris begins to appear. Cut reappears along the west as cut into the floor prep layer. Irregularity of width & depth of the cut might suggest earlier construction.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by Z Fox

Revised by CPM

PDFd by ECR

Entered by

on 7/25/11

on 29.7.11

on 3/8/11

on